

Use of NMMO Pretreatment for Biogas Production from Oil Palm Empty Fruit Bunch

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Abstract—Pretreatment of oil palm empty fruit bunch (OPEFB) with N-Methylmorpholine-N-oxide (NMMO) for enhancing biogas production was investigated. The pretreatments were performed at 90 and 120°C for 1, 3, and 5 h using 73, 79, and 85% NMMO. The pretreated OPEFB was subsequently anaerobically digested to produce biogas. After the pretreatment, there were no significant changes of the main composition of OPEFB and the maximum total solid recovery was 92%. The amorphous phase was increased up to 78% at pretreatment condition using 85% NMMO solution for 3 h at 120°C. In general, higher concentration of NMMO and higher temperature resulted in increased amorphous form and higher biogas production. The best result of biogas production after the pretreatment was 0.408 Nm³ CH₄/kg VS, which was 47.8% higher than that from untreated OPEFB.

Keywords—Oil palm empty fruit bunch, pretreatment, NMMO, biogas.

I. INTRODUCTION

Oil palm empty fruit bunch (OPEFB) is a lignocellulosic waste of palm oil industry that can be used as feedstock for biogas production. In 2010, Indonesia had crude palm oil (CPO) production of 23.6 million tons with annual OPEFB production of 6.8 million tons (dry base) [1], [2]. Biogas is an energy source that nowadays is used for cooking, heating, electricity production, and after upgrading as car fuel (e.g. [3]). Hence, utilization of OPEFB for biogas production has benefits in both an environmental point of view by alleviating solid waste accumulation in palm oil industry and in the production of renewable energy.

One important step in the conversion of OPEFB to biogas is the pretreatment process. Pretreatment aims to render the cellulose fraction so that it can be easily degraded during anaerobic digestion. Pretreatment methods include physical, chemical, physico-chemical, and biological methods (e.g.

[4]). Chemical pretreatments have shown to be very effective to increase digestibility of lignocellulosic materials for different purposes [5], [6]. In this work, the environmentally friendly solvent N-Methylmorpholine-N-oxide (NMMO) was used as the pretreatment reagent because it is non-toxic and can be recovered over 98% and reused [7]. NMMO has been proved to enhance biogas production from cellulose [8], rice straw, triticale straw, and softwood [9]. No literature was detected on pretreatment of OPEFB using NMMO for biogas pretreatment.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

Oil palm empty fruit bunch were obtained from palm oil company in Medan, Indonesia. It was shredded, sun-dried until the water content was 10%, and ground to a particle size of 40 mesh.

NMMO (50% w/w solution) was provided by BASF (Ludwigshafen, Germany). This solution was vacuum-evaporated to 73%, 79%, or 85% concentrations. Prior to the pretreatment, propyl gallate 0.6 g/l was added in order to avoid NMMO degradation during pretreatment [10]. The pretreatments were performed by soaking 6 g OPEFB in 94 g of 73%, 79%, and 85% NMMO solutions for 1, 3, and 5 h at 90 and 120°C with stirring in every 15 min up to pretreatment time was over. Then, 150 ml of boiled-distilled water was added into the mixture immediately. The pretreated OPEFB was then separated from the mixture by vacuum filtration and washed using hot water until a clear filtrate was obtained. The pretreated samples were used to determine weight loss, volatile solid, glucan, lignin, and crystallinity.

Batch anaerobic digestion experiments were carried out in 120 ml-serum glass bottles at thermophilic condition (55°C) for 50 days. The inoculum was obtained from a full-scale municipal solid waste digester, Sobacken (Borås, Sweden). Each bottle was filled with 27 ml of inoculum (0.4 g VS) and 3 ml of mixture of distilled water and NMMO-treated or untreated OPEFB as well as starch (Merck) as reference (0.15 g VS). Anaerobic digestion was also performed for blank sample that contained distilled water and inoculum. The anaerobic digestion experiments were run in triplicate.

National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) Analytical Procedures were used to determine the total solid [11], glucan [12], acid insoluble lignin [13], acid soluble lignin [14], and ash [15]. The crystallinity was examined using FTIR spectrometer (Impact 410, Nicolet Instrument Corp.,

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Madison, WI). Gas samples taken from the head space of glass digester were measured using GC (Varian 450-GC, USA).

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Effect of Pretreatment on Composition of OPEFB and Structure

The untreated OPEFB contained 41.16% glucan, 28.43% acid insoluble lignin, 3.40% acid soluble lignin, 5.35% ash, and 21.65% of xylan. After being pretreated using 73, 79, and 85% NMMO for 1, 3, 5 h, the results showed that the composition of glucan, acid soluble lignin, and acid insoluble lignin remained relatively constant (data not shown). During the pretreatment, NMMO penetrates into microfibrils and affect the recalcitrant of the biomass to less crystalline structure while maintaining the composition of lignocellulosic material [16]. However, ash content decreased from 5.35% to 1.94%. The ash of OPEFB contains several salts and metal ions, such as calcium, sodium, copper, and iron which can dissolve in water [17]. The decrease in ash content could have been caused by the addition of water and washing after the treatment. After the pretreatment, the total solid recovery of OPEFB was relatively high in the range of 89% and 92%.

The structural changes in OPEFB were studied by FTIR. The absorbance band at 1427 cm^{-1} and 898 cm^{-1} are assigned to cellulose I (crystalline form) and cellulose II (amorphous form), respectively. The FTIR spectra of pretreated and untreated cellulose (cf. Fig. 1) shows a reduction in crystalline cellulose I and increasing in amorphous cellulose II. During the pretreatment, NMMO binds to the hydroxyl group at the 2nd and 6th carbons in glucose polymers [18].

TABLE I

TOTAL CRYSTALLINITY INDEX

Temperature (°C)	Concentration of NMMO (%)	Time (h)	Total Crystallinity Index
90	73	1	0.60±0.07
		3	0.70±0.05
		5	0.65±0.03
	79	1	0.67±0.16
		3	0.66±0.05
		5	0.62±0.01
120	85	1	0.57±0.03
		3	0.57±0.05
		5	0.58±0.11
	73	1	0.57±0.03
		3	0.62±0.01
		5	0.61±0.08
79	1	0.58±0.02	
	3	0.60±0.07	
	5	0.61±0.01	
85	1	0.70±0.05	
	3	0.55±0.05	
	5	0.57±0.03	
Untreated OPEFB			2.50±0.08

When NMMO is removed during the washing, these chains will form a new bond in a reorganized state [19]. These phenomena might explain why crystalline cellulose of OPEFB was changed to the amorphous form after NMMO pretreatment.

Quantitatively, the degree of crystallinity is expressed by total crystallinity index (TCI), which was calculated based on the absorbance ratio A_{1427}/A_{898} (Table I). The TCI of OPEFB which was treated with 73% and 79% of at 120°C was lower than that of with 73% and 79% at 90°C . The best results were obtained when 85% NMMO solution was used. The pretreatment condition at 120°C using 85% NMMO

Fig. 1 FTIR spectra of pretreated and untreated OPEFB at 120°C . The spectra are for (1) 1 h, (2) 3 h, (3) 5h pretreatment, and (4) untreated

solution for 3 h resulted in the lowest TCI. By comparing TCI between the untreated OPEFB and the pretreated OPEFB with the lowest TCI, it can be calculated that the increase of the amorphous part was achieved up to 78%.

B. Biogas Production

All pretreated and untreated OPEFB were subjected to anaerobic batch digestion. Enhancement of methane yield

digestion compared to methane production of 0.443 Nm³ CH₄/kg VS from starch which was used as reference for 100% digestion.

The values of methane yield from the untreated and pretreated OPEFBs were in good agreement with results from other studies using lignocellulosic materials. For example, untreated paper tubes could produce 0.238 Nm³ CH₄/kg VS

TABLE II
METHANE PRODUCTION PROFILE FROM OPEFB TREATED WITH 85%NMMO

Pretreatment condition		Methane production profile					pH
Temperature (°C)	Time (h)	Initial rate ^a (Nm ³ CH ₄ /kg VS/day)	Yield (Nm ³ CH ₄ /kg VS)	Ratio yield ^b (%)	Ratio Enhancement ^c (%)	%CH ₄ ^d	
90	1	0.008±0.000	0.326±0.045	75.1	18.1	47.7	8.09
	3	0.011±0.000	0.360±0.000	81.3	30.4	48.4	8.17
	5	0.014±0.001	0.404±0.007	93.1	46.4	46.3	8.19
120	1	0.023±0.000	0.330±0.000	74.5	19.6	56.9	8.28
	3	0.030±0.003	0.408±0.000	94.0	47.8	55.0	8.27
	5	0.027±0.002	0.345±0.017	79.5	25.0	54.8	8.30
Untreated		0.012±0.003	0.276±0.002	63.6	0.00	55.4	8.26

^aMethane production rates during the first 10 days

$$\text{Ratio of yield (\%)} = \frac{\text{Yield of methane production from pretreated OPEFB}}{\text{Yield of methane production from Starch}} \times 100\%$$

$$\text{Ratio of enhancement (\%)} = \frac{(\text{Yield of methane production from pretreated OPEFB} - \text{Yield of methane production from untreated OPEFB})}{\text{Yield of methane production from Untreated}} \times 100\%$$

$$\text{\% CH}_4 = \frac{\text{Volume of methane}}{\text{Volume of methane and carbondioxide}} \times 100\%$$

was obtained for pretreated OPEFBs compared to the untreated one. In general, the methane yields from the pretreated OPEFBs using NMMO at 85% were relatively higher compared to that of at 73% and 79% NMMO (data not shown). The highest methane yield was 0.408 Nm³ CH₄/kg VS after OPEFB was treated with 85% NMMO solution for 3 h at 120°C. This value was an enhancement by 47,8% compared to methane production of 0.276 Nm³ CH₄/kg VS from the untreated OPEFB and this value corresponds to 94%

and after steam explosion with the addition of chemicals the paper tube residuals were reported to produce methane up to 0.493 Nm³ CH₄/kg VS [20]. Meanwhile, the use of NMMO to pretreat cotton linter for ethanol and biogas production showed that pretreatment using 73% NMMO could improve the biogas production to 0.413 m³ CH₄/kg VS in 15 days digestion [8]. It was an enhancement by 17% compared to 0.353 m³ CH₄/kg VS from the untreated cotton linter.

Fig. 2 and Table II show the methane production and its values from the pretreated OPEFBs using 85% NMMO at 90°C and 120°C. It can be observed that higher pretreatment temperature accelerated the initial biogas production rate that was measured during the first 10 days of anaerobic digestion. In this study, high enhancement in methane yield was achieved using 85% NMMO, which gave low crystallinity index (Table I) of the pretreated OPEFB. It is in line with the data presented in previous reports [21], showing that the presence of high amount of amorphous phase increased the degree of enzymatic hydrolysis rate. The amorphous celluloses provide larger accessible surface area and an easily-attacked substrate for the enzyme of hydrolytic bacteria, allowing the hydrolysis process to be performed faster. This would lead to increased digestibility of OPEFB and increased accumulated methane production.

Fig. 2 Accumulated methane production (Nm³/kg VS) after 10 (gray bars) and 50 days (black bars) of digestion from untreated OPEFB and treated OPEFB using 85% NMMO

IV. CONCLUSION

Pretreatment with NMMO is effective to enhance the digestibility of OPEFB and the methane yield during the

following biogas production. Major advantages of NMMO pretreatment that have been proved by this work are a) the composition of OPEFB after pretreatment did not change significantly b) small weight loss was detected after the treatment c) the treatment resulted in decreasing crystallinity of cellulose with increasing amorphous phase of OPEFB.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was financed by The International Program Office of Sweden and Swedish International Development Cooperation Agency (SIDA).

REFERENCES

- [1] USDA, *GAIN report: Indonesia oilseeds and products update*, USDA FAS, 2011.
- [2] DOA, *Report: Pedoman pengelolaan limbah industri kelapa sawit*, Jakarta: Department of Agriculture, 2006.
- [3] R. Sims, "Biomass and resources bioenergy options for a cleaner environment in developed and developing countries," London: Elsevier Science, 2003.
- [4] M. J. Taherzadeh and K. Karimi, "Pretreatment of Lignocellulosic Wastes to Improve Ethanol and Biogas Production: A Review," *Int. J. Mol. Sci.*, vol. 9, p. 1621-1651, 2008.
- [5] K. Mirahmadi, M. M. Kabir, A. Jeihanipour, K. Karimi, and M. J. Taherzadeh, "Alkaline pretreatment of spruce and birch to improve bioethanol and biogas production," *BioResources*, vol. 5, p. 928-938, 2010.
- [6] S. Abedinifar, K. Karimi, M. Khanahmadi, and M. J. Taherzadeh, "Ethanol production by *Mucor indicus* and *Rhizopus oryzae* from rice straw by separate hydrolysis and fermentation," *Biomass and Bioenergy*, vol. 33, p. 828-833, 2009.
- [7] M. E. Hall, A. R. Horrocks, and H. Seddon, "The flammability of lyocell," *Polym. Degrad. Stab.*, vol. 64, p. 505-510, 1999.
- [8] A. Jeihanipour, K. Karimi, and M. J. Taherzadeh, "Enhancement of ethanol and biogas production from high-crystalline cellulose by different modes of NMO pretreatment" *Biotechnology and Bioengineering*, vol. 105, p. 469-476, 2010.
- [9] A. Teghammar, K. Karimi, I. Sárvári Horváth and M. J. Taherzadeh, "Enhanced biogas production from rice straw, triticale straw, and softwood spruce by NMMO pretreatment," *Biomass and Bioenergy*, vol. 36, p. 116-120, 2012.
- [10] C.W. Kim, D. S. Kim, S. Y. Kang, M. Marquez, and Y.L. Joo, "Structural studies of electrospun cellulose nanofibers," *Polymer*, vol. 47, p.5097-5107, 2006.
- [11] T. Ehrman, *Standard method for determination of total solids in biomass*, NREL Midwest Res. Institute, pp. 7, 1994.
- [12] R. Ruiz, T. Ehrman, *Determination of carbohydrate in biomass by High Performance Liquid Chromatography*, NREL Midwest Res. Institute, 1996.
- [13] D. Templeton and T. Ehrman, *Determination of acid-insoluble lignin in biomass*, NREL Midwest Res. Institute, pp13, 1995.
- [14] T. Ehrman, *Determination of acid-soluble lignin in biomass*, NREL Midwest Res. Institute, pp. 7, 1996.
- [15] A. Sluiter, B. Hames, R. Ruiz, C. Scarlata, J. Sluiter, and D. Templeton, *Determination of ash in biomass*, NREL Midwest Res. Institute, 2005.
- [16] C. Cuissinat and P. Navard, "Swelling and dissolution of cellulose. Part 1: Free folating cotton and wood fibers in N-methylmorpholine-N-oxide-water mixtures," *Macromol. Symp.*, vol. 244, p. 1-18, 2006.
- [17] K. N. Law, W. R. W. Daud, and A. Ghazali, "Morphology and chemical nature of fiber strands of oil palm empty fruit bunch (OPEFB)," *Bioresources*, vol. 2, 351-362, 2007.
- [18] F. Wendler, A. Konkin, and T. Heinze, "Studies on the stabilization of modified lyocell solutions," *Macromol. Symp.*, vol. 262, p. 72-84, 2008.
- [19] Y. Zhao, Y. Wang, J. Y. Zhu, A. Ragauskas, and Y. Deng, "Enhanced enzymatic hydrolysis of spruce by alkaline pretreatment at low temperature," *Biotechnology and Bioengineering*, vol. 99, p. 1320-1328, 2007.
- [20] A. Teghammar, J. Yngvesson, M. Lundin, M. J. Taherzadeh, I. S. Horvath, "Pretreatment of paper tube residuals for improved biogas production," *Bioresource Technology*, vol. 101, p. 1206-1212, 2010.
- [21] R. Kumar, S. Singh, and O. V. Sing, "Bioconversion of lignocellulosic biomass: Biochemical and molecular perspectives," *J. Ind. Microbiol. Biotechnol.*, vol. 35, p. 377-391, 2008.